

Metal Complexes as Ligands : Polynuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel(II) Chelates

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Some nickel(II) complexes with O-N donor ligands (salicylaldoxime, glycine and β -alanine) and having oxygen-bridges with polymeric structures, depolymerise under suitable conditions and break up into monomers. These monomers *in situ*, behave as a single and double faced bidentate oxygen donor Lewis bases, and combine with partially covalent bonded alkali metal cations, to form oxygen-bridged polynuclear complexes. The spectral and magnetic moment studies indicate that the polymerised nickel(II) ions are converted into tetrahedral ones in their alkali metal adducts.

Nickel(II)-salicylaldoximate forms oxygen-donor five-membered stable chelate ring with alkali metal ions.

The area of homo- and hetero-polynuclear complexes has seen extensive growth, stimulated by interest in other areas and has been comprehensively reviewed^{1,2}. Reports of transition metal complexes, such as $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{salen})]$, (salen = N,N'-ethylene-bis(salicylideneimine)), may themselves act as partial coordinating spheres for alkali metals^{3a-h} are there. Banerjee *et al.* have reported^{4a-c} oxygen-bridged polynuclear complexes of alkali and alkaline earth metals using metal Schiff bases and β -diketonates as 'metal complex ligand'. The binuclear complexes are believed to form because of the ability of the salen phenolic oxygen atoms to function as bridging atoms. It has also been observed that these metallomers, which act as 'metal complex ligand' and are either dimers, trimers, tetramers or polymers and most likely depolymerise in presence of alkali metal salts; and these monomers act as Lewis bases and form stable compounds with suitable Lewis acids. The mechanism may be breaking of metal - oxygen bonds of the ligand metallomer *in situ*, forming monomer and leaving monomer oxygen atoms with further coordinative powers. This results the formation of oxygen-bridged hetero- or homopolynuclear complexes^{3d,4,5}. In the process, the geometry (with higher coordination number, usually six) of the central atom of

the metal in ligand metallomer, changes to lower coordination number, usually four in the hetero- or homo-polynuclear adducts formed by ligand metallomer ('metal complex ligand').

We have selected polymeric octahedral nickel(II) chelates, $[\text{NiL}_2]$, as 'metal complex ligands', and have extended the studies on oxygen-bridged complexes by synthesising a number of stable hetero-bimettallomer and -trimettallomer alkali metal adducts of the general formula, $[\text{NiL}_2\{\text{M}_a\text{L}'\}]$ or $[\text{NiL}_2\{\text{M}_a\text{L}'\}_2]$, where L = salicylaldoxime, glycine or β -alanine; $\text{M}_a = \text{Na}, \text{K}$; $\text{L}' =$ thiocyanate, deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol.

Results and Discussion

The results of analytical data (Table 1) of stable mixed adducts of alkali metal salts with bis(salicylaldoximate)-, bis(glycinato)- and bis(β -alaninato)nickel(II) denoted by $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-ala})_2$ respectively, showed that two molecules of alkali metal salts, $\text{M}_a\text{L}'$, combined with one molecule of $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ and the general formula of the adducts have been $[\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2(\text{M}_a\text{L}')_2]$; in the case of bis(glycinato)- and bis(β -alaninato)-nickel(II), these combined with one

TABLE I

Compd./ (Colour)	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		Ni	N	C	H	Na/K
Ni(SAO) ₂ (Light green)	240	17.68 (17.74)	8.42 (8.46)	49.60 (50.80)	4.12 (3.66)	-
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(Na1N2N) ₂ (Yellowish brown)	320	8.08 (8.14)	7.63 (7.77)	57.02 (56.61)	4.14 (3.36)	6.24 (6.37)
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(K1N2N) ₂ (Brown)	305	7.63 (7.79)	7.36 (7.44)	53.81 (54.19)	3.71 (3.22)	10.11 (10.38)
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(Na8HQ) ₂ (Yellowish green)	286	8.74 (8.82)	8.29 (8.42)	57.38 (57.77)	4.13 (3.64)	6.69 (6.91)
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(K8HQ) ₂ (Yellowish green)	295	8.23 (8.42)	7.79 (8.03)	54.88 (55.10)	3.89 (3.48)	11.19 (11.21)
Ni (gly) ₂ (Light green)	279	28.19 (28.39)	13.18 (13.54)	22.80 (23.21)	4.33 (3.89)	-
Ni(gly) ₂ .NaSCN (Light blue)	250	19.89 (20.39)	14.23 (14.59)	20.48 (20.84)	3.30 (2.80)	7.71 (7.98)
Ni(gly) ₂ .KSCN (Light blue)	225	18.80 (19.31)	13.62 (13.82)	19.38 (19.73)	3.24 (2.65)	12.59 (12.86)
Ni(gly) ₂ .Na8HQ (Light green)	302	15.32 (15.70)	10.84 (11.24)	40.90 (41.73)	4.12 (3.77)	5.89 (6.14)
Ni(gly) ₂ .K8HQ (Light green)	295	15.02 (15.05)	10.38 (10.77)	39.56 (40.00)	3.80 (3.61)	9.84 (10.02)
Ni(gly) ₂ .Na1N2N (Yellowish brown)	310	14.03 (14.61)	10.82 (10.45)	41.42 (41.80)	3.83 (3.51)	5.44 (5.72)
Ni(gly) ₂ .K1N2N (Brown)	290	13.80 (14.04)	10.47 (10.05)	39.60 (40.19)	3.92 (3.37)	9.02 (9.35)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ (Light green)	280	24.61 (25.00)	11.65 (11.92)	30.19 (30.66)	5.50 (5.15)	-
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .NaSCN (Light blue)	243	17.98 (18.58)	13.16 (13.30)	26.32 (26.59)	4.40 (4.14)	6.91 (7.27)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .KSCN (Light blue)	215	17.34 (17.68)	12.30 (12.65)	25.00 (25.30)	3.22 (3.64)	11.38 (11.77)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .Na8HQ (Greenish yellow)	210	14.32 (14.60)	10.04 (10.45)	44.40 (44.79)	4.90 (4.51)	5.31 (5.72)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .K8HQ (Yellowish green)	305	13.78 (14.04)	10.42 (10.05)	42.90 (43.06)	4.50 (4.34)	9.11 (9.35)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .Na1N2N (Yellowish brown)	290	13.32 (13.65)	9.90 (9.77)	44.42 (44.66)	4.65 (4.22)	5.20 (5.34)
Ni(β-ala) ₂ .K1N2N (Brown)	285	13.20 (13.16)	9.01 (9.42)	43.00 (43.05)	4.50 (4.06)	8.42 (8.76)

mole of M_2L' having the general formula $[Ni(\text{amino acid})_2.M_2L']$. The usual method of synthesis was to take alkali metal salts in absolute ethanol and Ni^{II} adducts added to it, usually in the molar ratio of 2:1 or 1:1 respectively, with slight excess of alkali metal salt. The mixture was refluxed for 4–6 h on a hot plate at 80° and then cooled. The resulting adducts were washed several times with absolute ethanol and dried at 100° . The colour of the adducts have

been found to be quite different from that of the 'complex ligand' and their decomposition temperatures have also been found to be higher than that of the corresponding 'complex ligands'. The adducts are stable under dried condition but decompose on exposure to moisture.

Infrared spectra : Infrared spectra (nujol) were measured in the range $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Selected absorption bands in different regions are given

TABLE 2

Compd	Mag. moment B.M.	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)		
		C=N/ SCN	N-O	
Ni(SAO) ₂	Diamag.	1 551	1 218, 1 204	1 023
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(Na1N2N) ₂	3.43	1 571	1 243, 1 230	1 040
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(K1N2N) ₂	3.48	1 569	1 245	1 042
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(Na8HQ) ₂	3.80	1 572	1 244, 1 234	1 040
Ni(SAO) ₂ .(K8HQ) ₂	3.69	1 570	1 242, 1 234	1 039
Ni(gly) ₂	3.06	-	-	1 584
Ni(gly) ₂ .NaSCN	3.58	2 081	-	1 576
Ni(gly) ₂ .KSCN	3.55	2 100	-	1 571
Ni(gly) ₂ .Na1N2N	3.87	-	-	1 590
Ni(gly) ₂ .K1N2N	3.72	-	-	1 587
Ni(gly) ₂ .Na8HQ	3.53	-	-	1 610
Ni(gly) ₂ .K8HQ	3.63	-	-	1 590
Ni(β -ala) ₂	3.18	-	-	1 597
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .NaSCN	3.52	2 100	-	1 580
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .KSCN	3.56	2 100	-	1 580
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .Na1N2N	3.73	-	-	1 590
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .K1N2N	3.70	-	-	1 589
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .Na8HQ	3.80	-	-	1 582
Ni(β -ala) ₂ .K8HQ	3.68	-	-	1 582

in Table 2. In bis(salicylaldoximate)nickel(II) the peak at 1577 cm⁻¹ of free salicylaldoxime due to C=N stretching vibration, is lowered⁶ to 1558 cm⁻¹. The spectra of the trinuclear alkali metal adducts of Ni(SAO)₂ chelate have been found to be of similar nature of AlPh₃ adducts⁷ of Ni(SAO)₂ chelate; and correspondingly C-O (phenolic), C=N and N-O frequencies are affected most when compared with nickel(II)-bis-salicylaldoximate. The frequencies reported⁶ at 1642 cm⁻¹ in nickel(II)-bis-salicylaldoximate, due to the OH groups, are not observed in the alkali metal adducts of the chelates. The absence of OH deformation vibration in that region in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts confirms that both the O-H-O hydrogen bonds of the complex ligand have been ruptured or may be bonded in different way in the alkali metal adducts. The C=N frequency of Ni(SAO)₂ observed at 1558 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 1557-1580 cm⁻¹ in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts. The characteristic absorption of C-O stretching vibration observed at 1023 cm⁻¹ in Ni(SAO)₂ shows upward shift in the range 1039-1042 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts. The fact that the

characteristic absorptions of the C=N groups are only very slightly affected by the substitution of the hydrogen, shows that this group does not change its reactivity. Since the C-O and C=N frequencies in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts of the chelates, shift to higher frequencies, it is suggestive that the electron delocalisation of the six-membered ring of complex ligand has been most probably did not remain delocalised, but likely to be localised at C=N and C-O bonds in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts. It is also suggestive that the hydrogen bonds, which are very short⁸ in the complex ligand, no longer remain bonded in that fashion in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts of the chelates. Thus the electrons involved in building the strong hydrogen bond are now most probably localised towards the C-O and N-O bonds in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts. Further, the N-O stretching vibrations observed at 1204 and 1218 cm⁻¹ in Ni(SAO)₂ show upward shift at 1230-1245 cm⁻¹ in the trinuclear alkali metal adducts of the Ni(SAO)₂. This displacement towards higher frequencies should be due to a polar structure, according to Blinc and Hadzi⁹.

The COO^- antisymmetric stretching frequency in anhydrous nickel glycinate (a polymer) is assigned at 1584 cm^{-1} . The CO^- antisymmetric stretching frequency assigned in the alkali metal adducts is usually found in the region $1571\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The fact that the characteristic absorptions of the COO^- group are only very slightly affected in the alkali metal adducts, shows that this group does not change its reactivity. In the alkali metal adducts the COO^- group is not free, if it would have been free (terminal ones), the frequencies are usually above 1700 cm^{-1} . So it is quite apparent that the carboxyl oxygen atoms which are bonded to other adjacent asymmetric unit in the metal glycinate chelate, are now no longer in that form but they are most likely attached to the alkali metals forming heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes. Only in case of Na8HQ adduct, it is found at 1610 cm^{-1} (broad), which of course does not show any agreement with the octahedral (six-coordinated with Na^+ outside the coordination sphere) environment of nickel(II) ion by absorption spectral study. Similarly, in case of $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-ala})_2$, the COO^- antisymmetric stretching frequency is assigned at 1597 cm^{-1} , whereas in the alkali metal adducts, the COO^- antisymmetric stretching frequency is assigned at $1580\text{--}1582\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It seems that when these nickel(II) glycinate and nickel(II) β -alaninate chelates, having an octahedral stereochemistry around the central metal ions, formed adducts with alkali metal salts, the attachment of carboxyl oxygen atoms, which were involved in satisfying the octahedral stereochemistry of the other adjacent asymmetric unit in the metal chelate, was broken, and simultaneously the carboxyl oxygen atoms are now attached to alkali metals. Hence the carboxyl group of amino acid unit, is most probably bridging between the alkali metals and the nickel metal of 'metal complex ligand'. In the alkali metal thiocyanate adducts, the thiocyanate ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) peaks at 2081 and 2100 cm^{-1} , shift to higher region (KSCN and NaSCN , 2020 cm^{-1}) suggesting their association¹⁰.

Magnetic susceptibility : In the present magnetic

investigation of $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ and their alkali metal adducts, it is found that square-planar diamagnetic complex $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ turned to paramagnetic in the alkali metal adducts and possess room temperature magnetic moment values between 3.43 and 3.80 B.M. (showing tetrahedral stereochemistry) (Table 2). Like $\text{Ni}(\text{DMG})_2$ (where one molecule is stacked one over the other in a staggered way forming a diamagnetic compound), $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ has the same structure and behaves in the same fashion^{4c} when it acts as a 'donor ligand'; but in $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ adducts of alkali metals, the structure changes from a polymer to a monomer, are tetrahedral and paramagnetic.

In the investigation of amino acids chelates of nickel(II), the observed magnetic values of anhydrous bis(glycinate)nickel(II) and bis(β -alaninate)nickel(II) are 3.06 and 3.18 B.M. respectively, which are almost equal to magnetic moment values observed by McAuliffe and Perry¹¹. The magnetic moment values of the isolated alkali metal adducts are found in the range 3.5–3.9 B.M. which is higher than those of the respective amino acids 'metal complex ligand' (Table 2). The higher magnetic moment values of alkali metal adducts of $\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\beta\text{-ala})_2$ may be due to change in the geometry of Ni^{II} environment of their respective amino acids 'metal complex ligand' from octahedral to tetrahedral structure.

Electronic spectra : The visible spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$, shows a broad absorption band at 526 nm, suggesting square-planar structure, which has been supported by its crystal structure¹². No absorption bands have been observed in the range 600–1500 nm. The spectrum of trinuclear alkali metal adducts are different in nature and the bands usually observed are at 575 and one weak broad at 1025 nm. The nature of bands in the alkali metal adducts suggests that the square-planar structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{SAO})_2$ has been converted into tetrahedral structure.

In the anhydrous nickel(II) complexes of glycine and β -alanine, the observed bands at 370, 625 and 1050 nm show typical octahedral stereochemistry of Ni^{II} environment. The spectral bands of the alkali metal adducts derived from Ni(gly)₂ or Ni(β -ala)₂ and found in the range of 600–665 nm (accompanying shoulder in the lower wavelength region in some cases) and a band of medium intensity observed around 1200 nm. The nature of absorption bands of alkali metal adducts suggests tetrahedral geometry of the Ni^{II} and the magnetic moment values observed higher than 3.4 B.M., further confirm the tetrahedral structure of Ni^{II} in the alkali metal adducts.

Concluding remarks : The fascinating observation revealed in this work, as noted earlier, is that polymeric 'metal complex ligand' in absolute ethanol media, in presence of partially covalent bonded alkali metal cation, suffers degradation. The alkali metal salt suffers slight hydrolysis and the solution becomes slightly alkaline. This alkalinity promotes degradation, and quite likely depolymerises these 'metal complex ligand' into monomers. These monomers *in situ*, behaves as single- or double-faced bidentate oxygen donor Lewis base and combine with partially covalent bonded alkali cation to form oxygen-bridged hetero-, di- or -trinuclear complexes. Ni(SAO)₂ when it functions as a 'metal complex ligand' forms oxygen-donor five-membered chelate ring with alkali metals; and as such are more stable than other 'metal complex ligands' which form oxygen-donor four-membered rings with alkali metals. These are easy to synthesise and separate, and all have appreciably higher decomposition temperatures than the 'complex ligand'. In the case of alkali metal adducts of Ni(SAO)₂, the alkalinity also helps in breaking strong in-

tramolecular hydrogen bonds, to form polymetal-olomers.

References

1. U. CASELLATO, P. A. VIGATO and M. VIDALI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 31.
2. S. E. GROH, *Israel J. Chem.*, 1976-7, **15**, 277.
3. (a) S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805; (b) E. SINN and C. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 391; (c) M. D. HOB-DAY and T. D. SMITH, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1973, **9**, 311; (d) G. H. W. MILBURN, M. R. TRUTER and B. L. VICKERY, *Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 1188; *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 841; (e) C. FLORIANI, F. CALDERAZZO and L. RANDACCIO, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1973, 384; (f) N. BRESCIANI-PAHOR, M. CALLIGARIS, P. DELISE, G. NARDIN, L. RANDACCIO, E. ZOTTI, G. FACHINETTI and C. FLORIANI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 2310; (g) L. G. ARMSTRONG, H. C. LIP, L. F. LINDOY, M. MCPARTLIN and P. A. TASKER, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1771; (h) G. FACHINETTI, C. FLORIANI, P. F. ZANAZZI and A. R. ZANZARI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 3002.
4. (a) A. K. BANERJEE, B. MAHAPATRA and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 778; (b) A. K. BANERJEE, M. K. GHOSH, S. K. SINHA and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 272; (c) A. K. BANERJEE, S. S. PRAKASH and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 53; (d) A. K. BANERJEE, D. PRASAD and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1303; (e) A. K. BANERJEE, D. PRASAD and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 9.
5. R. S. DRAGO, K. A. LESLIE, G. D. STUCKY, D. J. KITKO and J. A. BREESE, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 1885.
6. K. K. RAMASWAMY and G. I. JOSE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 156.
7. N. VOIENLESCU, I. POPESEN and N. LUCHIAN, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1973, **18**, 1601.
8. R. C. SRIVASTAVA and E. C. LINGAFELTER, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1967, **22**, 922.
9. R. BLINC and D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536.
10. R. K. GOSAVI, U. AGARWALA and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 235.
11. C. A. MCAULIFFE and W. D. PERRY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 634.
12. G. FACHINETTI and C. FLORIANI, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1974, 615.

